

Title: Hemoglobin is an oxygen-dependent glutathione buffer adapting intracellular redox state to oxygen availability

Short title: Hemoglobin as oxygen-dependent glutathione buffer

Authors

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Abstract

Fast changes in environmental oxygen (O_2) availability translate into shifts in mitochondrial free radical production and oxidative load that should be compensated by adequate immediate alterations in antioxidant defense mechanisms. This study explores the role hemoglobin (Hb) in oxygen-dependent modulation of reduced glutathione (GSH) levels in red blood cells. We have demonstrated that decrease in Hb oxygenation to 50% in twelve healthy humans while at high altitude, or in red blood cell suspension of healthy donors results in an increase in the intraerythrocytic GSH level that progresses with deoxygenation. Oxygen-dependent upregulation of the intracellular GSH was not associated with its de novo synthesis or release from S-glutathionylated cysteine residues of Hb molecules. Using isothermal titration calorimetry and in silico modelling, we have observed noncovalent binding of four molecules of GSH to oxy-Hb and the release of two of them from Hb upon deoxygenation and identified location of the binding sites within the Hb molecule. Oxygen-dependent binding of GSH to oxygenated Hb and its release upon deoxygenation occurs in antiphase with that of 2,3-bisphosphoglycerate. Furthermore, in the presence of GSH Hb shows increased O_2 affinity. Taken together, our findings have identified an adaptive mechanism by which red blood cells may provide advanced antioxidant defense to respond to oxidative challenges immediately upon deoxygenation.

Highlights

- Hypoxia causes an increase in reduced glutathione (GSH) in red blood cells
- Hemoglobin reversibly non-covalently binds GSH
- Oxy-hemoglobin binds four GSH molecules and deoxy-hemoglobin only two of them
- Hemoglobin deoxygenation results in release of GSH to resist oxidative stress.

Introduction

The main function of the most abundant cells in our body, red blood cells (RBCs), is to mediate oxygen (O_2) transport, and hemoglobin (Hb) is a key player in its execution. Apart from O_2 delivery, RBCs with their robust antioxidative defense system scavenge H_2O_2 and a function as a sink for oxidants produced by peripheral tissues under stress conditions, including hypoxia¹. Millimolar concentrations of reduced glutathione (GSH) contribute substantially to the antioxidative defense system, along with superoxide dismutase, catalase, and peroxiredoxins^{2,3}. GSH detoxifies oxidants by donating electrons while transforming into an oxidized state (GSSG). Glutathione may also form mixed disulfides with protein cysteines (S-glutathionylated adducts), protecting them from irreversible oxidation⁴ and prolonging lifespan of the circulating RBCs². In addition, S-glutathionylation of regulatory thiols in Hb and transmembrane proteins modifies the cellular rheology, membrane stability, and O_2 -carrying properties of RBCs⁵⁻⁷.

Changes in O_2 availability in the micro- and macro-environment are associated with acute local or systemic alterations in the redox state. A transient bout of free radical production in the mitochondria of most cells is a part of signaling cascade initiated in response to an acute hypoxic insult⁸. Prolonged continuous, or intermittent, hypoxia is associated with systemic oxidative stress⁹. Matching oxidative load and antioxidant defense capacity requires fast and flexible oxygen-dependent adjustments of the levels of antioxidants. Indeed, an acute dose-dependent increase in erythrocytic GSH levels in response to deoxygenation has been shown in mouse, rat, and human RBCs¹⁰⁻¹². The changes in GSH levels in RBCs upon prolonged hypoxic exposure depended on its severity and duration¹³⁻¹⁵.

The mechanisms behind this tuning of GSH levels to O_2 availability are currently unknown. Stimulation of the Embden Meyerhof pathway in response to deoxygenation is mediated by displacement of glycolytic enzymes from their docking sites on the cytosolic domain of band 3 protein by deoxyhemoglobin¹⁶⁻¹⁸. This metabolic switch diverts glucose from pentose phosphate shunt to the ATP production required for *de novo* GSH synthesis^{17,19}. However, an increase in GSH in RBCs upon deoxygenation does not rely on *de novo* GSH synthesis¹². The millimolar quantities of GSH emerging in the cytosol of deoxygenated RBCs by far exceed the amounts of GSH that may be recovered from the GSSG pool¹⁰, but are comparable with the amount of GSH that may be liberated in the course of massive de-glutathionylation of the six cysteine residues of Hb.

This study was undertaken to unravel the mechanisms of O_2 -dependent regulation of intraerythrocytic GSH in human RBCs. Herein, we demonstrate that Hb may function as an oxygen-sensitive buffer for GSH. Whereas oxyhemoglobin (oxy-Hb) binds four GSH molecules, two of them may be released into the cytosol during the transition from oxygenated to deoxygenated Hb conformation.

Materials and Methods

Blood samples and study participants

The study at high altitude was approved by the ethics committees of the University of Heidelberg, Germany, (S-066/2018) and the University of Bern, Switzerland (2018-01766). Twelve young male subjects took part in the study and blood samples were collected at sea level (SL) and high altitude (HA) (see Fig. 1A and ²⁰).

Venous blood samples of nine healthy donors of both genders were provided by the Clinical Laboratory of Cantonal Hospital Winterthur, Switzerland. These samples were used for calibration of blood analyzers (CO-oximetry included). In agreement with the Helsinki convention, healthy study subjects gave informed consent for blood donation. Li-heparin was used as anticoagulant.

Deidentified study participants' data that underly the reported results will be made available 3 months after the publication for a period of 5 years after the publication date at <https://zenodo.org/>.

Free intracellular GSH and GSSG measurement

GSH measurements were performed immediately after opening of the vacutainers with blood samples, in parallel to CO-oximetry. Ellman's reagent was used to determine the levels of GSH and GSSG in the incubated blood samples as described elsewhere^{12,21}.

Effect of hypoxic exposure on the intraerythrocytic GSH ex vivo

Oxygen-dependence of GSH levels in RBCs: RBC were washed in bicarbonate-containing plasma-like buffer BPLB (125mM NaCl, 25mM NaHCO₃, 4mM KCl, 1.8mM CaCl₂, 10mM glucose, 300μM L-Arginine, 300μM glutamic acid monosodium, 300μM glycine 10mM HEPES-imidazol (pH=7.40 at room temperature) and subsequently resuspended in BPLB and transferred into the Eschweiler tonometers. Buthionine sulfoximine (BSO, 1mM) was added to specific blood samples. Blood samples were pre-equilibrated with gas phase containing 15% O₂ for 30 min and then O₂ level was reduced to 0.5% O₂ and incubation continued for further 2 hours. Aliquots were collected at various time points to assess SO₂ with ABL825 FLEX blood analyzer and intracellular GSH and GSSG as stated above.

The impact of N-ethyl maleimide (NEM) on GSH release under hypoxic conditions: RBC were washed and resuspended in the plasma-like buffer (PLB). Incubation with NEM (20mM, 20 min) was used to derivatize reduced thiol groups and the excess of it was removed by triple-washing. RBC suspensions were subsequently placed into the Eschweiler tonometers and equilibrated with the air (21% O₂) or pure N₂ as gas phase at 37°C, and intracellular GSH levels and SO₂ were measured thereafter.

GSH levels in hemolysates treated with BPG: Washed RBC were resuspended in PLB and lysed by snap-freezing-thawing. Two lysate samples were placed into Eschweiler tonometers, and exposed to oxygenation-deoxygenation-reoxygenation exposure protocol (each step lasting 15 min). One of the samples was supplemented with 2 mM 2,3-bisphospho-D-glycerate (BPG) while deoxygenated-reoxygenated. SO₂ and GSH were detected in lysates at each condition.

Flow cytometry

For *ex vivo* deoxygenation experiments suspensions of RBC in BPLB were exposed to hypoxia (1% O₂) or normoxia (20% O₂) at 37°C for 3 h using Whitley H45 HEPA Hypoxystation or cell culture incubator respectively. RBCs were then loaded with fluorochromes to detect reduced thiols, reactive oxygen species, or NO for 30 min at 37°C in the same conditions (hypoxia or normoxia) in the darkness^{22,23}. Bulk intracellular reduced thiols were measured using monobromobimane (mBBr, 20 μM), ROS assessed using dihydrorhodamine (DHR, 7.5 μM) and N₂O₃ as a marker of NO was measured using 4,5-Diaminofluorescein diacetate (DAF-FM DA, 5 μM). After loading with the dyes suspensions were diluted with BPLB pre-equilibrated under hypoxic or normoxic condition and fluorescence was recorded using BD LSR Fortessa.

Samples from HA study were collected for detection of reduced bulk (non-protein and protein) thiols were detected by flow cytometry. Whole blood sample was loaded with 10 μ M mBBr, in plasma-like buffer supplemented with 0.1% bovine serum albumin for 1h in the darkness at room temperature²³ and RBC fluorescence was recorded using Gallios Flow Cytometer, BC.

Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC)

Purified Hb solution was prepared as follows. Human met-Hb (0.1 mM) was dissolved in 50 mM K-phosphate buffer (50 mM KCl, 34.8 mM K₂HPO₄, 15.2 mM KH₂PO₄, 2 mM MgCl₂, pH 7.4) and reduced using 5 mM sodium dithionite for 10 min. Reduced Hb was passed through the gel-filtration column (PD MiniTrap G-25). Elution was performed using 50 mM K-phosphate buffer. GSH (4 mM) and BPG (1 mM) were allowed to interact with oxy- or deoxy-Hb or Hb-GSH complex. The following sets of experiments were carried out: (i) titration of Oxy- or Deoxy-Hb with GSH, (ii) titration of Deoxy-Hb with BPG, (iii) titration of GSH-DeoxyHb complex with DPG, (iv) titration of Deoxy-Hb with BPG with the following titration with GSH. Detailed description of the experimental protocol and analysis of thermodynamic parameters may be found in the supplementary methods section.

The thermodynamic parameters for the GSH and BPG binding to Hb were determined using a MicroCal iTC200 and PEAQ-ITC, as described elsewhere (23).

Hemoglobin oxygen affinity measurement

Hb oxygen affinity of Hb in hemolysates prepared by freezing-thawing of RBC suspensions and mixed with PLB with or without GSH (5mM) supplementation was measured using Hemox analyzer (TCS Scientific, New Hope, PA).

Analysis of solvent-accessible surface area in Hb structures

Structures of oxygenated (5WOG; 5WOH and 1HHO), deoxygenated (1A3N; 2HHB and 2DN2) and of hemoglobin-BPG complex (1B86) were obtained from protein data bank (rcsb.org). Solvent accessible surface area (SASA) was calculated using Accessible Surface Area and Accessibility Calculation for Protein server and GETAREA server using a spherical water probe with a fixed radius (1.4 Å). Analysis of the cysteine S-groups positioning was performed using Moe2015.10 software.

Docking of GSH to Hb and Hb-BPG complex

For docking of GSH to Hb structures of human oxy-Hb and deoxy-Hb were obtained from the protein data bank (rcsb.org). For docking of GSH to Hb-BPG complex we have used the structure of human Deoxy-Hb–BPG complex (1B86) from the protein data bank (rcsb.org). Structures were pre-processed using the AutoDockTools program. Docking was performed using Autodock Vina. Moe2015.10 software was used for analysis of receptor-ligand interactions.

Investigation of the possible impact of deoxygenation on the Hb S-glutathionylation state

Blood samples collected from 12 study participants at sea level and high altitude (see **Fig. 1A** and ²⁰ for more details). Washed RBC pellet was snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C. Samples were thawed on ice and supplemented with a protease inhibitor cocktail (1:200) and 25 mM NEM in PBS to prevent oxidation of SH-groups. Negative control was prepared by treatment of a sample with 100 mM dithiothreitol. Primary mouse Anti-Glutathione antibody

(ab19534, abcam 1:1000) were used for detection of S-glutathionylated proteins and rabbit anti-human Recombinant Anti-Hemoglobin subunit beta/ba1 antibody (ab214049, Abcam 1:1000) for detection of hemoglobin. Densitometry was performed using Image studio lite (LI-COR Biosciences) and the signal for GSH was normalized to that for the β Hb monomer. Finally, the readouts obtained for different time points were normalized to the basal level of glutathionylation (time-zero for *ex vivo* experiments or samples before the HA exposure). Similar procedure was performed with RBC hemolysates obtained from RBC suspensions exposed to pure N₂ or air in Eschweiler tonometers at 37°C.

Statistics

Statistical analysis was performed using the R software²⁴ and GraphPad Prism. Shapiro-Wilk test was used for checking if the data were normally distributed. Subsequently, a parametric student's t-test or non-parametric Wilcoxon test was used to compare the two experimental groups. Specific details can be found in figure legends. Values are shown either as means \pm standard deviations or as boxplots with the minimum, the maximum, the sample median, and the first and third quartiles. To investigate the effects of the repeated measures in the *in vivo* HA study, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed with the study participant as a random factor. The differences between the 7 days were decomposed into four contrasts and tested on the level "day x study participant". The first contrast tested whether the dependent variable was different at high altitude compared to sea level (*p value < 0.05, **p value < 0.01, ***p value < 0.001). Then, the second contrast tested the difference between the two time points at high altitude (‡ p value < 0.05, ‡‡p value < 0.01, ‡‡‡p value < 0.001). Third, pre levels were compared to levels after return to sea level (†p value < 0.05, ††p value < 0.01, †††p value < 0.001) and the last contrast tested whether the days after return to sea level were different (¥).

Results

The effect of three weeks-long exposure to hypobaric hypoxia experienced at high altitude (HA) on RBC turnover in twelve healthy male students from Heidelberg was explored at Jungfraujoch research station in Switzerland (3500 m above sea level (SL)) as described by Klein et al²⁰ and schematically shown in **Fig.1A**. Exposure to HA was associated with an increase in Hb levels (**Fig. 1B**) and a decrease in Hb O₂ saturation (SO₂) of venous blood (**Fig.1C**) compared to the values at SL. At the same time, intracellular GSH levels in RBCs increased from 3.4 ± 0.65 to 4.6 ± 0.64 μ mol/g Hb (p<0.05), when at HA, and immediately returned to basal levels when the study participants returned to SL (**Fig.1D**). These changes were not accompanied by the reciprocal changes in GSSG of a corresponding size (within 0.5 μ mol/g Hb range) (**Fig.1E**). As a result, a reduction in the intraerythrocytic half-cell redox potential (E_{hc}) was observed under conditions of hypobaric hypoxia. Descent back to the SL was associated with recovery of E_{hc} back to the basal levels (**Fig.1F**). Plotting the data for intraerythrocytic GSH as a function of SO₂ revealed that dose-dependent exponential growth of intracellular GSH was only observed at a SO₂ below 50% (**Fig.1G**).

In line with these findings for the *in vivo* hypoxic exposure, gradual deoxygenation of RBCs resuspended in a plasma-like buffer using a gas mixture containing 0.5% O₂, 5% CO₂, and 94.5% N₂ resulted in a similar increase in intracellular GSH that was initiated when SO₂ reached 60-50% and progressed with deoxygenation (**Fig.2A**). Pre-treatment of RBCs with an inhibitor of *de novo* GSH synthesis did not prevent this hypoxia-induced rise in intracellular GSH (**Fig. 2A**, purple line). Both *in vivo* and *in vitro* deoxygenation of RBCs was not associated with a decrease in GSSG levels which could serve as a source of the GSH increase (**Fig. 2B**).

The upregulation in GSH levels in RBCs exposed to 1% O₂, 5% CO₂, and 94% N₂ for 3 h (**Fig. 3A**) was not associated with the changes in reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (**Fig. 3B**) but with an increase in NO levels (**Fig. 3C**). The O₂-dependent alterations in bulk (protein and non-protein) intraerythrocytic reduced thiol levels observed in RBC suspensions as monobromobimane fluorescence (**Fig. 3D**) were in agreement with the GSH measurements using Ellman's reagent (**Fig. 3A**).

Systemic exposure of our study participants to HA hypoxia for 3 days was associated with an increase in both bulk thiols in RBCs and intraerythrocytic GSH levels. However, after 3-week-long stay at HA bulk thiols were decreased compared to the basal level, whereas GSH levels in RBCs remained upregulated (compare **Fig. 1D** and **Fig. 3E**). Oxidation of protein thiols was not accompanied by an accumulation of methemoglobin (**Fig. 3F**).

We hypothesized that covalently- or noncovalently-bound GSH could be deposited within oxy-Hb and released upon a conformational transition during deoxygenation. Availability of cysteine residues α -102, β -112, and β -93 for S-glutathionylation was modelled *in silico* for the oxy- and deoxy-Hb. Modelling revealed that the thiol group of the β Cys93 is inwardly facing in oxy-Hb but translocates into an outwardly facing position as Hb deoxygenates (**Fig. 4A**). If GSH is bound to this thiol group, its de-glutathionylation is only possible when Hb is in deoxygenated state and glutaredoxin 1 may approach it (**Table S1**). The thiol group of the α Cys102 is unavailable for S-glutathionylation and that β Cys112 is available to bind or release GSH independent of Hb oxygenation state follows from the analysis of solvent accessible surface area (**Table S1**).

To verify if the changes in Hb oxygenation are associated with an alteration to the S-glutathionylation of Hb molecules (HbSSG), immunoblotting of Hb harvested from oxygenated and deoxygenated RBCs in suspension was performed (**Fig. 4B**). A similar approach was used to compare HbSSG abundance in the blood of study participants after 3 weeks at HA and when at SL (**Fig. 4C**). RBCs treated with dithiothreitol were used as a negative control. Both acute (minutes) and long-term (days) exposure to hypoxia did not produce a change in HbSSG in RBC lysates *in vitro* or *in vivo*.

In order to exclude the possibility of de-glutathionylation as a source of GSH release at low O₂ tension, RBCs were pre-treated with N-ethylmaleimide (NEM) prior to deoxygenation. This allowed blocking all the reduced thiol groups of GSH available in the oxygenated cells. The excess of non-conjugated NEM was removed by multiple washing steps and then the control and the NEM-pretreated RBCs were deoxygenated (**Fig. 4D**). Results shown in figure **4E** indicate that pre-treatment with NEM abolished an increase in GSH levels in response to deoxygenation, indicating that the released GSH molecules were stored within the protein in reduced form and not as S-glutathionylated adducts or as GSSG (**Fig. 4F**). Furthermore, conjugation of GSH with NEM promoted the oxidation of Hb to methemoglobin (**Fig. 4G**).

These findings suggested that, if occurring, the docking of GSH to Hb does not involve covalent binding to protein thiols. Complex formation of GSH with oxy-Hb and deoxy-Hb was detected using isothermal titration calorimetry (**Fig. 5A,B**). The thermodynamic parameters such as the changes in enthalpy (ΔH), in entropy ($T\Delta S$), and in Gibbs energy (ΔG), equilibrium association and dissociation constants K_a and K_d , and stoichiometry of interactions were obtained in these experiments (**Fig. 5C**). Oxy-Hb was shown to bind four molecules of GSH, whereas deoxy-Hb could only bind two of them. Affinity of deoxy-Hb to GSH ($K_d=17 \mu\text{M}$) was lower than that of the oxy-Hb ($K_d=2 \mu\text{M}$) and the entropic component prevailed in the binding energy profile (**Fig. 5C**). This indicates that the binding can be attributed primarily to hydrophobic interactions.

In silico modelling was used to identify the amino acid residues involved in non-covalent docking of GSH to Hb (**Table S2** and **Fig. 5D**). In oxy-Hb, two pairs of “pockets” were found, each binding a single GSH molecule. The first pair of binding sites is located at the interface between the two β -globins, and the second pair of sites with slightly lower affinity is located between the two α -globins, both pairs of sites spaced within the central cavity (**Fig 5D**).

Amino acids predicted to be involved in GSH interaction with Hb are listed in supplementary **table S2**. The following key conservative amino acids were predicted to form each of four sites shown in **Fig. 5D** (site 1: β_1 Val1, β_1 Leu81, β_1 Ala140, β_1 His146, and β_2 Leu81, β_2 Ala140, β_2 His146; site 2: β_1 His146 and β_2 Ala138, β_2 His146; symmetrical sites 3 and 4: α_1 Val1, α_1 Leu2, α_1 Pro95, α_1 Phe98, α_1 His103, α_1 Asp126, α_2 Tyr 140, β_1 Val 34, β_1 Trp37, β_1 Asn108, β_1 Val109). Upon deoxygenation and transformation from oxy-Hb to deoxy-Hb, the “pockets” with two GSH between two β -globin chains opens, allowing for the release of two GSH molecules from docking sites 1 and 2 (**Fig. 5D**, and **movie M1**).

The central cavity of Hb harbors a binding site for 2,3-bisphosphoglycerate (BPG) which binds at the β - β globin interface. *In silico* modelling was performed to predict if the BPG and GSH binding sites interfere with each other (**Fig. 6C**). Docking of GSH to the complex deoxy-Hb-BPG indicated that the binding sites for BPG and GSH do not overlay spatially.

The prediction was confirmed by a competition experiment where oxygenated hemolysates were incubated with a mixture of GSH and BPG or with GSH alone and then deoxygenated. As follows from figure **6A-B**, the presence of BPG does not compromise hypoxia-induced GSH release from Hb. K_d values and stoichiometry of GSH binding to complex deoxy-Hb-BPG did not differ significantly from GSH binding to deoxy-Hb (**Fig. 6D**, **Table S3**). Thus, BPG did not influence the GSH binding sites of deoxy-Hb. Based on the ITC data and on the modelling predictions, two out of four GSH molecules occupying the sites 1 and 2 leave the Hb cavity during the transition from oxy-Hb to deoxy-Hb. Some of the amino acids forming BPG binding site in deoxy-Hb were predicted to be a part of the GSH site 1. However, site 1 is not existing in deoxy-Hb conformation and, thus, no competition exists between GSH and BPG for binding to Hb. Docking of GSH to the sites 3 and 4 in deoxy-Hb did not interfere with BPG-deoxy-Hb complex formation (**Fig. 6E,F**) but caused reduction in the enthalpy component and an increase in the entropy contribution to BPG binding with deoxy-Hb (**Table S3**). This indicates a decrease in the contribution of Van-der-Waals and hydrogen interactions and an increase in the contribution of hydrophobic interactions to the BPG-deoxy-Hb complex formation (**Fig. 6 E-F**, **Table S3**). Taken together, these findings indicate that GSH and BPG bind each to their own binding site in the central cavity of deoxy-Hb. While the *in silico* modelling suggested that the binding site of BPG in oxy-Hb was occupied by GSH upon interaction with site 1 (Fig 6C), we could not provide experimental evidence for that since the binding constant for BPG to oxy-Hb was below the detection limit of ITC.

Finally, the impact of GSH on O_2 dissociation from Hb was assessed in RBC lysates. The addition of 5mM of GSH to the lysates resulted in a small but consistent reduction in $p50$, indicating an increase in Hb O_2 affinity (**Fig. 6G**)

Discussion

This study revealed a new function for Hb as a regulator of intracellular free GSH levels making redox potential of RBCs O_2 -sensitive. Furthermore, the formation of a non-covalent complex between Hb and GSH has an impact on the thermodynamics of BPG interaction with the protein (**Table S3**). Recent studies revealed that the central cavity of Hb is a multi-ligand docking site for several molecules. Those include organic phosphates, $NAD(P)H^{25}$, and GSH. Binding sites

for all negatively charged allosteric modulators share some common amino acids (**Table S2**). For example, Val1 of the β -chain is a common binding partner for Cl⁻, BPG, and GSH (site 1) and Lys82 for BPG and GSH (site1) binding. The probability for a particular ligand to bind to the central cavity of Hb depends on pH, temperature, ligand's concentration and affinity, and the presence of competing ligands²⁶.

Cytosolic Hb concentration (5.4mM) is comparable with that of GSH (2-3.5mM) and BPG (2-7mM, depending on the severity of hypoxia)^{27,28,29} whereas the concentrations of NADH (10⁻⁴ mM) and NADPH (10⁻² mM) are lower and comparable with GSSG levels³⁰. Under conditions of chronic O₂ deprivation such as HA exposure, the concentration of BPG rises²⁹. This increases the probability for BPG to bind to Hb even in an oxygenated state and would compromise O₂ loading in the lungs, even though its affinity to oxy-Hb is low (Kd=4.75mM for oxy-Hb vs 0.1mM for deoxy-Hb³¹). Maintenance of effective O₂ binding in the lungs and its release into the peripheral tissues is essential for survival under hypoxic conditions. As follows from our findings (**Fig. 6**), BPG binding to deoxy-Hb is not compromised by GSH and *vice versa*, and the release of GSH from Hb during deoxygenation is not altered by BPG. The increase in SO₂ to 50% or more (**Fig. 1G, 2A**) will result in binding of GSH to sites 1 and 2 and interference with BPG binding to Hb, thus promoting O₂ binding to Hb in hypoxic lungs (**Fig. 6G, H**). When reaching the hypoxic periphery, GSH is released from the cavity, and BPG binds to the high affinity site (**Fig. 6H**). The deoxygenation threshold for release of GSH according to our measurements *in vitro* is about 50% SO₂. This threshold is achieved in venous blood during exercise when arterio-venous difference in SO₂ increase from 28% to 79%³². In part, the release of GSH from Hb upon deoxygenation may explain the observed arterio-venous difference in intraerythrocytic GSH¹⁰.

Fast binding and release of GSH from the “pockets” within Hb occurs already while passing from arteries to capillaries and veins, as a difference in GSH content was reported between RBCs harvested from venous and arterial blood^{10,12}. Liberation of GSH from deoxy-Hb provides advanced antioxidant defense without extra energy expenditure (in contrast to *de novo* production of GSH or reduction of GSSG to GSH) to combat an increase in intracellular (**Fig. 3B**) and systemic^{8,33} ROS production upon deoxygenation. Thus, instead of depletion of the GSH or bulk reduced thiols' pools, their upregulation is observed in deoxygenated RBCs (**Fig. 3A, 3D**). Prolonged periods of systemic hypoxia, however, promote the development of uncompensated oxidative stress condition (e.g. **Fig. 3E**,³⁴).

Although we could not confirm the O₂-dependent changes in HbSSG levels in our study, this source of GSH is there in RBCs and most likely may be used under harsh conditions such as smoking and disease (chronic renal failure, iron deficiency anemia, hyperlipidemia, diabetes mellitus, Friedreich's ataxia, atherosclerosis). All these pathologies were reported to be associated with advanced S-glutathionylation of Hb^{35,36}. Similar to noncovalent binding of GSH to Hb, its S-glutathionylation was shown to increase Hb O₂ affinity^{37,38,39}.

This study urges further investigation of the physiological role of GSH pools non-covalently bound to Hb in health and disease. Detection of intraerythrocytic GSH levels should include its correction for Hb O₂ saturation. Finally, we may expect that depletion of the Hb-GSH pool would reflect the severity of chronic uncompensated oxidative stress.

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Figure legends

Figure 1: The impact of high altitude on the selected blood parameters and intraerythrocytic redox state (A) Study design with days of blood sampling. numbers in the arrows are the days of the study counted from ascent to the HA. Colors for the time of blood sampling (red for basal level, blue for HA exposure and grey for the time after descent from HA) are used in all the other plots. (B) Hemoglobin levels, and (C) SO₂ measured by ABL825 FLEX, Radiometer. (D) intracellular GSH and (E) GSSG levels measured by Ellman's reagent. (F) Redox potential calculated as $E_{hc} \text{ (mV)} = -240 - \left(\frac{59.1}{2} \times \log \frac{[GSH]^2}{[GSSG]}\right)$, at 25 °C, pH 7.0, from ⁴⁰ (G) Association between SO₂ and GSH levels. Blue line is a fit using the method of loess (Local Polynomial Regression Fitting), the grey area shows the confidence interval (95%). Statistics: N=12, ANOVA with custom contrast: * HA different from pre/sea level; ‡ different HA03 and HA18; † different pre and sea level. *HA: High altitude (3500m), SL: sea level (110m), GSH: reduced glutathione, GSSG: oxidized glutathione, SO₂: hemoglobin oxygen saturation.*

Figure 2: Recycling from GSSG and de novo synthesis do not explain the increase in GSH levels upon deoxygenation. (A) Intraerythrocytic GSH levels as a function of SO₂ in RBC suspension (N=7). Grey curve is for untreated control, and pink curve is for RBC pretreated for 20 min with the inhibitor of *de novo* GSH synthesis BSO (L-Buthionine-sulfoximine, 1mM). (B) GSSG levels in RBCs as a function of SO₂ (N=9). *Abbreviations identical to Fig. 1.*

Figure 3: The impact of deoxygenation on redox balance in RBCs *ex vivo* and *in vivo*. The effect of incubation of RBC suspensions at 1% hypoxia for 3h on: (A) GSH levels measured by Ellman's reagent. (B) ROS levels detected using DHR (C) NO levels measured using DAF-DA and (D) bulk reduced thiols detected using MBBR staining. N=6, paired Wilcoxon test in Graph Pad. Impact of HA exposure on the bulk thiol levels detected as MBBR fluorescence (E) and metHb levels measured using ABL825 FLEX, Radiometer (F). For more details on the HA study design see Fig1A. N=12, ANOVA with custom contrast: * HA different from pre/sea level; ‡ different HA03 and HA18; † different pre and sea level. *MBBR: monobrombimane, NO: nitric oxide, ROS: reactive oxygen species, DHR: dihydrorhodamine, DAF-DA: diamino fluorescein diacetate.*

Figure 4: Testing for oxygen-dependent changes in Hb S-glutathionylation: (A) Modeling of the possible changes in availability of Cys residues α Cys102, β Cys93, and β Cys112 for S-glutathionylation. Shown is a superposition of oxy-Hb(blue) and deoxy-Hb(red) structures with a blow-up of the areas where Cys are localized. While thiol group of β Cys93 is facing outwards in the deoxy-Hb, it is turned inwards into the Hb molecule in the oxy-Hb state. Position of the thiol groups of α Cys102 and β Cys112 is not altered by oxygenation-deoxygenation. (B) S-glutathionylation of Hb in RBC suspension that were gradually deoxygenated in a tonometer in the atmosphere of 100% N₂. Aliquots were taken after 2, 5, 10, and 20 minutes and SO₂ shown above the plot was measured by ABL825 FLEX, Radiometer. RBC were lysed in non-reducing lysis buffer supplemented with NEM (25mM) and S-glutathionylation of Hb as well as β -globin detected using specific antibodies. Representative blots obtained for one of the RBC samples is shown at the upper panel. Densitometry for the S-glutathionylated form of Hb monomers normalized to that for the β -globin is shown at the lower panel. Paired Wilcoxon test was used for analysis. N=8. (C) Similar approach was used to assess S-glutathionylation of Hb in blood samples of participants from the HA study. Representative immunoblot is shown for one participant before, during and after the staying at HA Statistics: ANOVA with custom contrast * different from pre/sea level and high altitude. N=12 (D) Schematic representation of NEM

experiment. (E-G) RBC were pretreated with NEM (20mM) or control and incubated for 20min. Samples were washed and incubated either in air (21% O₂) or 100% N₂ for 30min. GSH levels were measured by Ellman's reagent. (D) GSH levels (E) GSSG levels (F) Methemoglobin levels measured by ABL825 FLEX, Radiometer. Paired Wilcoxon test. N=7. *NEM: N-ethyl maleimide. RBC: red blood cell, DTT: 1,4-Dithiothreitol, HBB: Hemoglobin subunit beta, GSH: Glutathione*

Figure 5: Noncovalent binding of GSH to Hb is O₂-dependent: Original representative recordings for the GSH titration curves for (A) oxy-Hb and (B) deoxy-Hb obtained using isothermal titration calorimetry. (C) Quantification of the titration curves for 3 independent experiments. Shown are the number of binding sites for GSH per 1 molecule Hb (N), and association and dissociation equilibrium constants K_a and K_d, and the thermodynamic parameters of Hb-GSH interaction ΔH , $-T\Delta S$ and ΔG . (D) Best Hb-GSH docking models produced by Vina Autodock docking. Upper panel shows the front and side views for the best four affinity GSH binding sites in the oxy-Hb, and lower panel shows the same for the deoxy-Hb. Beta chains are shown in brown and the alpha chains are in blue. Shown in pink are GSH molecules occupying the sites 1-4 and the GSH molecules in green interact with the sites 3 and 4 in deoxy-Hb. ΔH : the changes in enthalpy, $-T\Delta S$: the changes in entropy, and ΔG : the changes in Gibbs energy.

Figure 6: The interplay between GSH and O₂ binding to Hb. (A-B) RBC hemolysates were allowed to interact with GSH in the presence or absence of 5 mM BPG. Free GSH was detected in hemolysates incubated in the atmosphere of 21% O₂ (normoxia dotted line) for 10 min and then deoxygenated in 100% N₂ (hypoxia dashed line). Then, 5 mM BPG was added to half of the samples and the lysates allowed to interact with it for further 15 min (hypoxia bars). Subsequently, the lysate was reoxygenated for 15 min (normoxia bars) Red bars are for BPG-treated samples, grey bars are for reoxygenated control and blue bars are for deoxygenated control (A) shows free GSH levels and (B) those for free GSSG levels in lysates. N=3. (C) . Models showing interactions of GSH with BPG-Hb complex (front and side views). Alpha chains are shown in light grey, and β chains are in dark grey. GSH molecules are highlighted in red, and BPG molecules are in green. (D-F) Original recordings and titration curves for the following conditions obtained using isothermal titration calorimetry at 25 °C (D) docking of GSH to deoxy-Hb-BPG complex (E) docking of BPG to deoxy-Hb (F) docking of BPG to deoxy-Hb in the presence of GSH. Quantification of these curves is in Table S3. (G) P50 values obtained for hemolysates in the absence or presence of 5 mM GSH measured by Hemox analyser. (H) Schematic representation of a possible mechanism of changes in docking partners for Hb in RBCs during deoxygenation-reoxygenation (for details, see the text). *BPG: 2,3-bisphosphoglycerate, P50: the oxygen tension when hemoglobin is 50 % saturated with oxygen*

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

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Sample	Ligand	N	K_a , M^{-1}	K_d , μM	ΔH , kcal/mol	$-T\Delta S$, kcal/mol	ΔG , kcal/mol
oxyHb	GSH	4.1	4.8×10^5	2.1	-0.13	-7.63	-7.76
deoxyHb	GSH	2.4	0.59×10^5	17.0	-0.23	-6.28	-6.51

D

Figure 5

Figure 6

Hemoglobin is an oxygen-dependent glutathione buffer adapting intracellular redox state to oxygen availability

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Supplementary Materials and Methods

Blood samples and study participants

The study at high altitude was approved by the ethics committees of the University of Heidelberg, Germany, (S-066/2018) and the University of Bern, Switzerland (2018-01766). Twelve young male subjects took part in the study and blood samples were collected at sea level and high altitude (see Fig. 1A and ²⁰).

Venous blood samples of nine healthy donors of both genders were provided by the Clinical Laboratory of Cantonal Hospital Winterthur, Switzerland. These samples were used for calibration of blood analyzers (CO-oximetry included). In agreement with the Helsinki convention, healthy study subjects gave informed consent for blood donation. Li-heparin was used as anticoagulant. Hemoglobin oxygen saturation SO₂, hemoglobin (Hb) concentration, and methemoglobin was measured on a blood gas analyzer (ABL825 FLEX, Radiometer) immediately after opening of the vacutainer.

Deidentified study participants' data that underly the reported results will be made available 3 months after the publication for a period of 5 years after the publication date at <https://zenodo.org/>.

Free intracellular GSH and GSSG measurement

GSH measurements were performed immediately after opening of the vacutainers with blood samples, in parallel to CO-oximetry. Ellman's reagent was used to determine the levels of GSH and GSSG in the incubated blood samples as described elsewhere ^{12,40}. Briefly, whole blood (in vivo study) or RBC suspension (ex vivo experiments) was diluted 5X in ice cold 5% Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) solution and deproteinized during a 30min incubation on ice. TCA and low temperature provide optimal conditions for prevention of GSH oxidation ¹⁰. Denatured Hb and other proteins were pelleted by centrifugation for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatant containing non-protein thiols was collected and pH in it was adjusted to neutral with saturated Tris-OH solution (Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, Biosolve, 200923). The samples were then used for GSH and GSSG detection. The 200 µl aliquot of supernatant was diluted 800 µl in GSH buffer (100mM Na₂HPO₄, 10mM Na₂EDTA, Sigma). For the measurement of total GSH (GSH and GSSG), glutathione reductase (10µg/mL, Sigma G6004) and NADPH (β-Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide 2'-phosphate reduced tetrasodium salt hydrate, Sigma N1630) at final concentration of 40 µM were added to the diluted samples. Finally, DTNB (5,5'-Dithiobis(2-nitrobenzoic acid), Sigma D8130) at final concentration of 10 µM was added and the resulting samples incubated for 3 min at room temperature. The absorption was measured

before (blank) and after incubation with DTNB at 412nm on a Lambda 25 UV/VIS spectrometer (Perkin Elmer) and blank values were subtracted. A calibration curve was produced with reduced GSH (Sigma, G4251) diluted in 0.1 N HCl and used to calculate the concentration of GSH in the sample that was then normalized to hemoglobin concentration (measured by Drabkin's reagent (Hemoglobin transformations solution, LCN 043 Dr Lange, Hach Lange GmbH, Berlin, Germany). All chemicals used in this study were from Merck if not stated otherwise.

Effect of hypoxic exposure on the intraerythrocytic GSH ex vivo

Oxygen-dependence of GSH levels in RBCs: RBC were washed in bicarbonate-containing plasma-like buffer (125mM NaCl, 25mM NaHCO₃, 4mM KCl, 1.8mM CaCl₂, 10mM glucose, 300µM L-Arginine, 300µM glutamic acid monosodium, 300µM glycine 10mM HEPES-imidazol (pH=7.40 at room temperature), all reagents from Sigma-Aldrich) and centrifuged at 1700xg for 5min for 3 times. The washed red blood cells were diluted in the bicarbonate-containing plasma-like buffer to about 30% hematocrit and transferred into the Eschweiler tonometers. Buthionine sulfoximine (BSO, Sigma B2515) at final concentration of 1mM was added to specific blood samples. First, samples were fully oxygenated for 30min with a humidified gas mixture of 15% O₂, 5% CO₂ and 80% N₂. Subsequently, the gas mixture was changed to 0.5% O₂, 5% CO₂ and 94.5% N₂ and incubated for up to 2 hours. At different time points (0, 30, 60, 120min) an aliquot was collected and analysed for hemoglobin oxygen saturation using CO-oximeter function of the blood gas analyser ABL825 FLEX, (Radiometer). Reduced and oxidized glutathione (GSH and GSSG) levels were detected in the samples by Ellman's reagent.

The impact of NEM on GSH release under hypoxic conditions: RBC were washed three times in the plasma-like buffer and spun at 1700 x g for 5min. The resulting RBC pellet was resuspended in plasma-like buffer to a hematocrit of 30%. The alkylating agent NEM (20mM) was used to derivatize reduced thiol groups and incubated for 20 min at room temperature and subsequently triple-washed in plasma-like buffer and resuspended to a hematocrit of about 30%. The same procedure was performed for the control sample without the addition of NEM. Subsequently, the samples were placed into the Eschweiler tonometers and equilibrated with the air (21% O₂) or pure N₂ as gas phase at 37°C until RBCs were fully oxygenated or deoxygenated. Glutathione levels were detected by a colorimetric assay (Ellman's reagent), and hemoglobin SO₂ controlled using ABL825 FLEX blood gas analyser (Radiometer).

GSH levels in hemolysates treated with BPG: Washed RBC were resuspended in plasma-like buffer to a hematocrit of 20%. The cells were destroyed by snap-freezing in liquid N₂. Two 4 ml-samples of the resulting lysates were re-oxygenated in two tonometers for 20 min. Aliquots of each oxygenated lysate (0.4 ml) were collected for measurements of SO₂ and GSH at time zero. Thereafter the atmosphere in the tonometers was switched to pure N₂ and lysates were deoxygenating for 15 min before the next aliquot was collected for SO₂ and GSH detection. Thereafter, one of the samples was supplemented with 2,3-Diphospho-D-glyceric acid penta(cyclohexylammonium) salt (BPG) at a final concentration of 2 mM, and deoxy-Hb in lysates was allowed to interact with BPG for 15 min before the SO₂ and GSH measurements were repeated. Thereafter, the samples were reoxygenated for 20 min and the SO₂ and GSH were detected in a final set of aliquots.

Flow cytometry

Ex vivo deoxygenation experiments: RBC were washed twice with the bicarbonate-containing plasma-like buffer: 125 mM NaCl, 25mM NaHCO₃, 4mM KCl, 0.75mM MgSO₄ and 0.015mM ZnCl₂, 10mM glucose, 100μM L-Arginine, 200μM glutamic acid monosodium, 200μM glycine, 0.2mM Alanine, 0.6mM Glutamine, 20mM HEPES-imidazole, pH 7.4 at RT. RBC were pelleted at 1500g during 10 min. Then RBC were diluted in the same medium to about 30-40% hematocrit, divided into two parts, and transferred into the hypoxic chamber (95% N₂, 4.5% CO₂, 1% O₂, 37°C) (Whitley H45 HEPA Hypoxystation) or into the cell culture incubator (20% O₂, 5% CO₂) at 37°C. Samples were incubated for 3 h, after that 1 μl RBC suspension was mixed with 99 μl of the extracellular medium bicarbonate-containing plasma-like medium and fluorescent probes were added to the samples to detect reduced thiols, reactive oxygen species, ROS or NO^{41,42}. Bulk intracellular reduced thiols were measured using monobromobimane (mBBBr, 20 μM), ROS assessed using dihydrorhodamine (DHR, 7.5 μM) and N₂O₃ as a marker of NO was measured using 4,5-Diaminofluorescein diacetate (DAF-FM DA, 5 μM). RBCs were loaded with the fluorescent probes for 30 min at 37°C in the same conditions (hypoxia or normoxia) in the darkness. Thereafter, RBC was diluted by buffer equilibrated under hypoxic or normoxic condition and fluorescence was recorded using flow cytometer BD LSR Fortessa.

Samples from HA study: Reduced bulk (non-protein and protein) thiols were detected by flow cytometry (Gallios, Beckman Coulter or LSRFortessa, Becton Dickinson). Whole blood (2uL) was added to the 1ml staining solution consisting of 10 μM mBBBr, (ThermoFisher M1378) in Plasma-like buffer supplemented with 0.1% bovine serum albumin,⁴²). Cells were incubated for 1h in the darkness at room temperature. Thereafter, RBC fluorescence was assessed. Data analyses were performed using the Kaluza software (Beckman Coulter).

Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC)

Purified Hb solution was prepared as follows. Human Hb (Sigma H7379 lot #SLCJ0443) was dissolved in 50 mM K-phosphate buffer (50 mM KCl, 34.8 mM K₂HPO₄, 15.2 mM KH₂PO₄, 2 mM MgCl₂, pH 7.4) at concentration of 0.1 mM. As the purified protein was in metHb state, reduction was performed with 5 mM (from the 1M stock in H₂O) sodium dithionite (Dia-m). After 10 min of incubation, 500 μL of 0.1 mM reduced Hb was passed through the gel-filtration column (PD MiniTrap G-25; GE Healthcare). Elution was performed using 600 μL of 50 mM K-phosphate buffer. The column was preliminarily equilibrated with 50 mM K-phosphate buffer. GSH stock solution (40 mM) was prepared on the same buffer and used at a final concentration of 4 mM for the ITC experiment. Stock solution of DPG (100 mM) was prepared on 50 mM K-phosphate buffer and used at the concentration of 1 mM. Hb-GSH complex was prepared by mixing of 670 μM GSH to 75 uM Deoxy-Hb. The following sets of experiments were carried out: (i) titration of Oxy- or Deoxy-Hb with GSH, (ii) titration of Deoxy-Hb with DPG, (iii) titration of GSH-DeoxyHb complex with DPG, (iv) titration of DeoxyHb with DPG with the following titration with GSH.

Experiments were performed in the normoxic atmosphere of 21% O₂ (air), or under hypoxic conditions (1% O₂). To achieve hypoxia the ITC system was placed into a hypoxic chamber (Whitley H45 HEPA Hypoxystation) to reach stable deoxygenating conditions (99% N₂, and 1% O₂). Prior to the experiment under hypoxic conditions all the buffers and the column were equilibrated with the atmosphere of hypoxic chamber overnight. All manipulations with Hb during its preparation were also performed in hypoxic atmosphere.

The thermodynamic parameters for the GSH and BPG binding to Hb were determined using a MicroCal iTC200 instrument (GE Healthcare) and PEAQ-ITC (Malvern Pananalytical), as

described elsewhere (23). Experiments were carried out at 25 °C in a 50 mM K-phosphate buffer. Aliquots of the ligand (GSH, 2.0 µl, 4 mM) were injected into the cell containing 70-100 µM Hb to obtain a complete binding isotherm. Aliquots of the BPG (2.0 µl, 1 mM) were injected into the measurement cell containing 70-100 µM deoxyHb to reach a complete binding isotherm. To detect the effective heat of binding, the heat of dilution was subtracted from the heat of the reaction. The resulting titration curves were fitted using the MicroCal Origin and Malvern software, assuming one set of binding sites. Equilibrium association (Ka) and dissociation (Kd) constants and the enthalpy change (ΔH) were determined, and the changes in Gibbs energy (ΔG), and the entropy change (ΔS) were calculated from equation $\Delta G = -RT \ln K_a = \Delta H - T\Delta S$.

Hemoglobin oxygen affinity measurement

Hb oxygen affinity was measured using Hemox analyzer (TCS Scientific, New Hope, PA). Blood samples were washed in PBS and resuspended to a hematocrit of about 30%. Then, the cells were lysed by freezing in liquid nitrogen.

Two buffers were prepared and adjusted to pH of 7.2. The first buffer was PBS that was used as a control and the second buffer was supplemented with 5mM GSH. Five ml of the buffer in the cuvette of the Hemox analyzer was supplemented with 20 µL hemolysate were added and the oxygen dissociation curve (ODC) was recorded at 37°C. The data was analyzed using the R software and the p50 were calculated where the oxygen saturation of Hb was 50%.

Analysis of solvent-accessible surface area in Hb structures

Structures of oxygenated (5WOG; 5WOH and 1HHO), deoxygenated (1A3N; 2HHB and 2DN2) and of hemoglobin-BPG complex (1B86) were obtained from protein data bank (rcsb.org). Solvent accessible surface area (SASA) was calculated using Accessible Surface Area and Accessibility Calculation for Protein server (Center for informational biology, Ochanomizu University, <http://cib.cf.ocha.ac.jp/bitool/ASA/>) and GETAREA server (Sealy Center for Structural Biology, University of Texas Medical Branch, <http://curie.utmb.edu/getarea.html>) (43) using a spherical water probe with a fixed radius (1.4 Å). Analysis of the cysteine S-groups positioning was performed using Moe2015.10 software.

Docking of GSH to Hb and Hb-BPG complex

For docking of GSH to Hb structures of human oxy-Hb (1hho; 1lfq; 1lft; 1lfv; 1lfy; 1lfz; 1r1x; 5wog; 5woh; 6bb5) and deoxy-Hb (1a3n; 1b86; 1bij; 1bz0; 1bzz; 1c7b; 1c7c; 1g9v; 2dxm; 4hhb) were obtained from the protein data bank (rcsb.org). For docking of GSH to Hb-BPG complex we have used the structure of human Deoxy-Hb-BPG complex (1B86) from the protein data bank (rcsb.org). Structures were pre-processed using the AutoDockTools program (The Scripps Research Institute). Docking was performed using Autodock Vina. Moe2015.10 software (was applied for analysis of receptor-ligand interactions).

Investigation of the possible impact of deoxygenation on the Hb S-glutathionylation state

Ex vivo hypoxia: RBC were washed in a plasma-like buffer and centrifuged at 1700xg for 5min for 3 times. Washed RBC were resuspended in plasma-like buffer to a hematocrit of 30% and incubated in the atmosphere of pure N₂ or air in Eschweiler tonometers at 37°C. Aliquots of RBC suspensions were collected after 0, 2, 5, 10 and 20 min of incubation and analyzed for SO₂ using CO-oximetry module of the ABL825 FLEX blood gas analyzer (Radiometer). S-glutathionylation of hemoglobin monomers was assessed by immunoblotting. The aliquot of the suspension (40µL) was diluted in 200 µL non-denaturing lysis buffer (137mM NaCl, 1%

Nonidet P-40 (Fluka 74385), 2mM EDTA, 20mM Tris-HCl pH 8) supplemented with a protease inhibitor (1:200) and N-ethylmaleimide (NEM, 25mM, Sigma 04259). The alkylating agent NEM was used to derivatize reduced thiol groups to avoid further oxidation. The samples were incubated on ice for 30 min and centrifuged at maximal speed for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatant was stored at -20°C until further analysis.

In vivo hypoxia: Blood samples collected from 12 study participants at sea level and high altitude (see **Fig. 1A** and ²⁰ for more details). Plasma and buffy coat were removed, and the RBC pellet was snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C. Samples were thawed on ice and the alkylating agent N-ethylmaleimide (NEM, Sigma 04259, 25mM) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS; 137mM NaCl, 2.7mM KCl, 10mM Na₂HPO₄, 1.76mM KH₂PO₄) was added to derivatize reduced thiol groups to prevent artifactual oxidation in sample preparation.

To produce a negative control sample the lysate was treated with 100 mM dithiothreitol (DTT) in PBS. Thereafter 15µL of negative and control samples were mixed with 400uL PBS supplemented with 25mM NEM. Hemoglobin concentration in the resulting samples was detected using Drabkin's solution ⁴³. One volume of hemolysate was mixed with the five volumes Laemmli buffer ⁴⁴ without β-mercaptoethanol and 10µg of protein were loaded on a 14% acrylamide gel, separated by SDS-PAGE and transferred to the nitrocellulose membrane. The membrane was fixed in 0.4% Paraformaldehyde in PBS for 30min. Subsequently, the membrane was blocked with 5% milk in Tris-buffered saline containing 0.1% Tween-20 (TBS-T; 150mM NaCl, 50mM TrisHCl, 0.1% Tween-20) for 30 min and incubated with the primary mouse Anti-Glutathione antibody (ab19534, abcam 1:1000) in 5% BSA/TBS-T was incubated for 1h. Thereafter, the membrane was washed three times for 5 min with TBS-T and incubated with horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated secondary antibody in TBS-T for 30 min. The membrane was washed in TBS-T and developed using HRP substrate (32109, ThermoFisher), 10 sec). The GSH-associated signal was visualized on ChemiDoc™ Imaging System (BioRad). Subsequently the membrane was washed 5 min in TBS-T and incubated with primary rabbit anti-human Recombinant Anti-Hemoglobin subunit beta/ba1 antibody (ab214049, Abcam 1:1000) in 5% BSA/TBS-T) for 1h with the following incubation with the corresponding anti-rabbit secondary antibody. Densitometry was performed using Image studio lite (LI-COR Biosciences) and the signal for GSH was normalized to that for the βHb monomer. Finally, the readouts obtained for different time points were normalized to the basal level of glutathionylation (time-zero for ex vivo experiments or the signal obtained for the blood samples before the exposure to HA).

Statistics

Statistical analysis was performed using the R software (R version 3.6.1, R Core Team (2019). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>) and GraphPad Prism. Shapiro-Wilk test was used for checking if the data were normally distributed. Subsequently, a parametric (student's t-test) or non-parametric test (Wilcoxon test) was used to compare the two experimental groups. Specific details can be found in figure legends. Values are shown depending on their distribution either as means ± standard deviations or as boxplots with the minimum, the maximum, the sample median, and the first and third quartiles. To investigate the effects of the repeated measures in the in vivo study at high altitude, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed with the study participant as a random factor. The differences between the 7 days were decomposed into four contrasts and tested on the level "day x study participant". The first contrast tested whether the dependent variable was different at high altitude compared to sea level (* p value < 0.05, ** p value < 0.01, *** p value < 0.001). Then, the second contrast tested the difference between the two time points at high altitude (‡ p value

< 0.05, †† p value < 0.01, ††† p value < 0.001). Third, pre levels were compared to levels after return to sea level († p value < 0.05, †† p value < 0.01, ††† p value < 0.001) and the last contrast tested whether the days after return to sea level were different (¥).

Fig. S1.

Figure S1. Docking of glutathione to the Hb molecule. A. Front and side views of superposition of oxy- and deoxy-Hb-GSH docking models. GSH molecules in pink are shown docked to the oxy-Hb. GSH docked to deoxy-Hb is shown in green. Alpha chains are shown in light blue (oxy-Hb) or dark blue (deoxy-Hb). Beta chains are in light brown (oxy-Hb) and brown (deoxy-Hb) B. The statistical analysis of hemoglobin residues involved in Hb-GSH complex formation by docking experiments.

Table S1

A

Oxyhemoglobin				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	5WOG	0 Å ²	2.917 Å ²	2.395 Å ²
	5WOH	0 Å ²	1.308 Å ²	2.592 Å ²
	1HHO	0 Å ²	1.383 Å ²	2.696 Å ²
AV		0	1.869	2.561
SD		0	0.908	0.152
Deoxyhemoglobin				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	1A3N	0 Å ²	13.010 Å ²	1.348 Å ²
	2HHB	0 Å ²	12.813 Å ²	1.348 Å ²
	2DN2	0 Å ²	13.285 Å ²	2.489 Å ²
AV		0	13.036	1.728
SD		0	0.237	0.658
Deoxyhemoglobin in complex with DPG				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	1B86	0 Å ²	11.144 Å ²	2.904 Å ²

B

Oxyhemoglobin				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	5WOG	0 Å ²	2.72 Å ²	2.56 Å ²
	5WOH	0 Å ²	1.57 Å ²	2.60 Å ²
	1HHO	0 Å ²	1.23 Å ²	2.59 Å ²
AV		0	1.84	2.583
SD		0	0.78	0.02
Deoxyhemoglobin				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	1A3N	0 Å ²	11.08 Å ²	1.46 Å ²
	2HHB	0 Å ²	10.97 Å ²	1.71 Å ²
	2DN2	0 Å ²	11.00	2.29 Å ²
AV		0	11.01	1.82
SD		0	0.05	0.42
Deoxyhemoglobin in complex with DPG				
Cys residue		α Cys104	β Cys93	β Cys112
Structure reference (PDB id).	1B86	0 Å ²	8.98 Å ²	2.73 Å ²

Tab. S1: Surface accessible to solvent in oxy-Hb and deoxy-Hb structures.

Using Accessible Surface Area and Accessibility Calculation for Protein server (A) and GETAREA server (B) we calculated solvent accessible surface area (SASA) which is characterized by the geometrical exposure (Å²) of amino acid residue atoms to the spherical water probe with a fixed radius (1.4 Å) rolling over a molecule and represents the free space around the single residue. β Cys93 has the different SASA in oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin structures. Presented data suggests that α Cys104 is inaccessible both hemoglobin states, SASA of β Cys112 remains comparable in all hemoglobin structures.

Binding site IDs	Beta	Alpha	References
GSH Site 1 (only for Oxy-Hb)	β_1Val1, β_1Leu81, β_1Lys82, β_1 Gly136, β_1 Asn139, β_1Ala140, β_1His143, β_1His146 β_2Leu81, β_2Lys82, β_2 Gly136, β_2 Asn139, β_2Ala140, β_2His143, β_2His146		
GSH Site 2 (only for Oxy-Hb)	β_1 Glu101, β_1 Arg104, β_1 Asn139, β_1 Ala142, β_1His146 β_2 Glu101, β_2 Phe103, β_2 Arg104, β_2Ala138,	α_1 Val96	

Table
S2

	β_2 Asn139, β_2 Ala142, β_2His146		
GSH Site 3 (for Oxy- and Deoxy- Hb)	β_2Val34 , β_2 Tyr35, β_2Trp37 , β_2 Leu105, β_2Asn108	α_1 Thr137, α_1 Ser138, α_1Tyr140 , α_2Val1 , α_2Pro95 , α_2 Val96, α_2Phe98 , α_2 Lys99, α_2 Ser102, α_2His103 , α_2 Leu106, α_2Asp126 , α_2 Lys127, α_2 Leu129, α_2 Ala130, α_2 Ser131, α_2 Ser133, α_2 Thr134, α_2 Thr137	
GSH Site 4 (for Oxy- and Deoxy- Hb)	β_1Val 34 , β_1 Tyr35, β_1Trp37 , β_1 Arg104, β_1 Leu105, β_1 Leu106, β_1Asn108 , β_1Val109	α_1Val1 , α_1Leu2 , α_1Pro95 , α_1Phe98 , α_1 Lys99, α_1 Ser102, α_1His103 , α_1 Leu106, α_1Asp126 , α_1 Lys127, α_1 Leu129, α_1 Ala130, α_1 Ser131, α_1 Thr134, α_1 Thr137, α_1 Ser138 α_2 Thr137, α_2Tyr140	
DPG	Val1 , His2 , Lys82 , His143 , Lys86	S187, K202, H206, K209	(1, 2)
NADH/ATP	A82 , K90/ K61	S187, K202, H206, K209	(2)
Cl ⁻	Val1 , His2, His82	Ser131	(3)

Table S2: GSH binding site on the hemoglobin structure. Conservative residues are in bold.

References for the Table S2

1. H. F. Bunn, J. H. Jandl, Control of hemoglobin function within the red cell. *N Engl J Med* **282**, 1414-1421 (1970).
2. A. Parashar, V. D. Jacob, D. A. Gideon, K. M. Manoj, Hemoglobin catalyzes ATP-synthesis in human erythrocytes: a murburn model. *J Biomol Struct Dyn*, 1-13 (2021).
3. H. Mairbaur, R. E. Weber, Oxygen transport by hemoglobin. *Compr Physiol* **2**, 1463-1489 (2012).

Table S3

Sample	Ligand	N	K _a , M ⁻¹	K _d , μM	ΔH, kcal/mol	-TΔS, kcal/mol	ΔG, kcal/mol
deoxyHb+DPG	GSH	1.8	0.38×10 ⁵	26.5	-0.26	-5.99	-6.25
deoxyHb	DPG	0.41	3.3×10 ⁵	3.0	-1.00	-6.48	-7.48
deoxyHb+GSH	DPG	0.46	1.9×10 ⁵	5.2	-0.38	-6.83	-7.21

Table S3 Thermodynamic parameters of the DPG and GSH binding to Deoxy-Hb determined by isothermal titration calorimetry at 25 °C.

K_a – equilibrium association constant, standard deviation did not exceed ±20%;

K_d – equilibrium dissociation constant; calculated as K_d = 1/K_a;

ΔH – enthalpy variation; standard deviation did not exceed ±10%;

TΔS – entropy variation; standard deviation did not exceed ±10%;

ΔG – Gibbs energy; Calculated from the equation: ΔG=-RTlnK_a;

Movie M1. Docking of GSH and BPG to the hemoglobin molecule in the oxy and deoxy state.

Oxy-Hb contains four bound GSH molecules inside the cavity, two of them at the β - β interface (sites 1 and 2) and two at the α - α chains interface (sites 3 and 4). In deoxy-Hb, two GSH molecules from the β - β subunits interface are released from the sites 1 and 2 allowing BPG to bind. Reoxygenation of Hbb is associated with release of BPG from its binding site and binding of two GSH molecules to the sites 1 and 2. The sites 3 and 4 remain occupied by GSH independent of the Hb conformation.